

METHODS OF A MODERN APPROACH IN ORGANIZING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK

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Annotation. The article discusses modern approaches to the organization of independent work of students in higher education, forms of organization of independent work, methods that develop independent work and their significance, issues of improving the skills of independent work.

Key words: self-study, student, self-study, mathematical problem, forms, computer, frontal, psychologist, teacher, didacticist, methodologist.

TALABALAR MUSTAQIL ISHINI TASHKIL ETISHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUV USULLARI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada talabalarning oliy ta'limda mustaqil ishlashni tashkil etishda zamonaviy yondashuv usullari, mustaqil ishni tashkil etish shakllari, mustaqil ishlashni rivojlantiruvchi usullar va ularning ahamiyati, mustaqil ishlash ko'nikmasini takomillashtirish masalariga ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: mustaqil ta'lim, talaba, mustaqil tadqiqot, matematik muammo, shakllar, kompyuter, frontal, psixolog, pedagog, didaktik, metodist.

МЕТОДЫ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ПОДХОДА В ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ СТУДЕНТОВ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются современные подходы к организации самостоятельной работы студентов в высшей школе, формы организации самостоятельной работы, методы, развивающие самостоятельную работу и их значение, вопросы совершенствования навыков самостоятельной работы.

Ключевые слова: самостоятельное обучение, студент, самостоятельное исследование, математическая задача, формы, компьютер, фронтал, психолог, педагог, дидакт, методист.

Independent research work in mathematics aims to increase students' interest in acquiring knowledge and prepare them for practical activities based on academic knowledge. Why is this or that scientific-theoretical information being taught to students, when and in what situations can this knowledge be applied? questions such as. [4]

They will be able to find answers to these questions as a result of solving real life problems. When solving mathematical problems, they rely on their previous knowledge and, of course, feel the need to further expand their knowledge. With the help of the teacher, students determine the directions of activity. Students search for solutions to mathematical problems and obtain specific results. Explaining and showing through examples that each mathematical problem, i.e. example or problems, to which the answer is sought, is a solution to a problem in nature, science or practical life, increases students' interest in science. I think it is difficult to find a field where mathematics does not play any role. It is known that the further development of sciences is characterized by the introduction of mathematical methods and mathematical thinking into them. At first glance, mathematics may seem like a dry and uninteresting subject. But if you pay attention, we face mathematical problems every day in our practical life. We all know that mathematics

is an exact science, so learning this science, whether you are from Uzbekistan or a representative of another country, its importance does not choose time and place. Today, we cannot imagine our life without various gadgets and the Internet. The basis of the creation of these things can be explained by the solution of several mathematical problems. Teaching students every mathematical problem related to practical life causes the subject to take a firm place in their minds and their interest in science will increase even more. This interest creates the ground for them to study independently. Below, we have given a simple example of one of the cases of the elements related to geometry in our daily life. This diagram can be understood not only by professionals related to mathematics, but also by every member of our society. [5]

The following forms are used to organize students' independent work

Above, we mentioned the forms of organizing independent work. If we want to teach these things to students, it is better to have an innovative approach to this subject rather than such usual tables. If we use information technology achievements as much as possible, we will increase the efficiency of our work. Today, we cannot imagine the educational and cognitive process of students without information technologies. Independent reading is an integral part of the learning process. You can quickly and easily find information on the topics you are interested in through the Internet. Tables can be animated using **Canva** software. Although this table does not differ in terms of content from the usual table, its appearance and design are displayed in harmony with the pictures that match the information provided. This increases the interest in learning in every learner. The help of the computer system in obtaining knowledge, that is, in searching for certain types of information, is incredibly great. Regardless of how information is presented, the importance of computer technology in collecting, storing, processing and using it is not a secret to any of us. First, the use of new information technologies in teaching accelerates the learning process compared to the standard (traditional) system, increases the student's interest in science, increases their creative activity, facilitates a differential approach to education, repetition, consolidation and control of acquired knowledge. makes the student a subject of the learning process.

Secondly, it will be possible to use new information technologies in the educational process in the following ways:

- computer lessons in teaching specific subjects;
- computer lessons as visual material;
- in the organization of group and frontal work of students;
- in the organization of students' scientific research;
- solving the issues of proper organization of students' free time from studying, etc.

With the introduction of informatization in our republic, every citizen in it has the opportunity to receive information at the right time, in the right amount, and in the right quality.

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